

The ANALYST project: Strengthening the integrated approach of holistic impact assessments for Safe and Sustainable by design plastic value chain

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Building on the early principle of Safe by Design (SbD), the concept of Safe and Sustainable by Design (SSbD) has evolved over the years, shaped by various European projects and activities into the comprehensive framework we know nowadays. In response to growing global environmental concerns, SSbD expanded the SbD principles to incorporate sustainability, creating a more holistic approach. This evolution culminated in the European Commission's 2023 formal recommendation on SSbD, which provides structured guidelines and methodologies to support its implementation.

In this context, the Horizon Europe project ANALYST, focuses on advancing the transition toward safer and more sustainable industrial value chains, particularly within the plastic sector. It contributes to the advancing of the SSbD framework by developing robust methodologies and tools for holistic impact assessments covering environmental, health, social, and economic factors. Key innovations include the ANALYST-BOX, a methodology for PVC impact assessment; ANALYST-DIGI, a digital platform for decision-making support; and ANALYST-T-PACK, a validation program with real-world use cases in the automotive and construction sectors. The project aims to support informed investment, align with EU policies like the Green Deal, and foster a paradigm shift towards cleaner and more sustainable industrial practices.

Intelligent testing strategies and a tiered approach to the SSbD framework are essential for generating new data and addressing the complexity of chemical and material innovation. Non-animal-based new approach methodologies (NAMs), including *in vitro* and *in silico* methods, are pivotal for innovative, exposure-led, and hypothesis-driven hazard and risk assessments. However, clear guidelines on which methodologies and tools to use, whether alone or in combination, during different stages of the SSbD assessment are still lacking.

As part of the ANALYST project, the state of the art in hazard and risk assessment methodologies relevant to SSbD was scoped through a review of published and grey literature, as well as unpublished research presented at conferences and workshops. This foundational work is driving the creation of the ANALYST-toolbox, a collection of methodologies and guidelines designed to integrate SSbD practices into industrial workflows. The toolbox will be tested across three practical cases within the PVC and plastic value chain, aiming to operationalize the SSbD framework effectively.

By facilitating this integrated approach, the ANALYST project seeks to empower the industrial sector to transition towards inherently safe and sustainable chemicals, materials, and products, supporting a broader paradigm shift.